

Distribution and Assessment of fresh water Avifaunal Diversity from Ranjeet Sagar Dam and Kuhmaar Ke Naade Talab of Kekri, District, Rajasthan

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Abstract

The present study was carried out to distribution and assessment of fresh water avifaunal diversity at two fresh water bodies of Kekri district, Rajasthan. Observation suggested that total that total 52 species of birds belong to 18 families and 10 orders were found at Ranjeet Sagar Dam and total 44 species of birds belong to 17 families and 8 orders Kuhmaar Ke Naade Talab, The present study also used the diversity indices for assessment the present status of avian diversity in study area. Both selected study sites has approximate same values and has good population of birds and it should be protected by government agencies.

Keywords Assessment, Avian Diversity, Kekri District.

Introduction

Biological environment is the environment where the life form can exists. The sum of environments where the life forms exists is called the Biosphere, these includes a portion of land, water and air. Biological environment includes the Habitat (Place where the organism lives) and natural surroundings of all species (living organism species) of the particular area. Biodiversity is the variety among living organisms and their interaction within ecosystems. Species diversity is a key component to healthy ecosystems. Biodiversity is also the basis of innumerable environmental services that keep us and the natural environment alive - from the provision of clean water and watershed services to the recycling of nutrients and pollination. Biodiversity (Species diversity) is the most characteristic feature of the nature which includes ecological communities (viz. Animals, Plants and Human species). Birds serve as one of the best environmental indicators. Their presence anywhere speaks volumes of the environment as to whether all is well or there is something amiss. (Meena, *et al.*, 2018) The main objective of the present study is to observe, document and evaluate during primary field survey carried out within 10 km radius in and around the enhancement to understand the presence and behaviour of the floral and avifaunal diversity of the study area with respect to water birds and water associate birds with special emphasis on Rare, Endangered and Threatened species occurring in and around the study area at Village: Pranheera, Bhimravas, Kanchariya, Khawas, Sheshpura and Dev Kheda District: Kekri, Rajasthan.

Objective of study

Little information is available about present of aquatic avifaunal status of small permanent water bodies in district Kekri, Rajasthan. Therefore, the present study provides a comprehensive check-list of birds to identify the current status of aquatic avifaunal diversity of Kekri District of Rajasthan State.

Review of Literature

Avifaunal diversity also shows the biological importance or going technical, the biodiversity significance of an area (Harney and Bhute, 2014). During the last few decades considerable studies on avifauna diversity from different freshwater bodies of India have been carried out by researchers like, Davidar (1985), Mujumdar (1984), Newton *et al.* (1986), Jhingram (1988), Rathore and Sharma (1999), Yardi *et al.* (2004), Kulkarni *et al.* (2005), and Kumar (2006), Donar *et al.* (2012) Meena, *et al.* (2018), Dutt, (2023). However very little information is available about present of aquatic avifaunal status of small permanent water bodies in district Kekri, Rajasthan.

Therefore, the present study provides a comprehensive check-list of birds to identify the current status of aquatic avifaunal diversity of Kekri District of Rajasthan State.

Methodology

Study location: The present study of waterbird and water associate avifaunal diversity was studied in Kekri district and nearby two satellite permanent water bodies (Ranjeet Sagar Dam and Kuhmaar Ke Naade Talab), parts of district Kekri of Rajasthan state. It is situated 80 Km far from Ajmer and 130 Km from Jaipur capital of Rajasthan. Its coordinates are 25°58'29.40" North and 75°09'10.71" East. Elevation is 1188 ft. Observations regarding avifaunal diversity at Ranjeet Sagar Dam and Kuhmaar Ke Naade Talab was recorded during one year period.

Fig. 1. Map and satellite image showing the study area, Kekri, district, Rajasthan.

Sampling

Study sites were observed by the visual encounter method. Transects were plotted along the periphery of the water body, observation were started from the start point to the end point to cover all the periphery area of the water body of interest. Only the avian faunal diversity which encountered in transect were noted and the species outside transects were left out according to the standard protocols. The stretch of transect was limited to shallow water towards depth water and the range of visibility of opposite side.

Statistics Used in the Study

Table No. 4: Family wise distribution of of avian diversity recorded at Ranjeet Sagar Dam and at Kuhmaar Ke Naade Talab.

Table No. 5: Diversity Index values of avian diversity recorded at Ranjeet Sagar Dam and Kuhmaar Ke Naade Talab

Diversity Index	Result at Ranjeet Sagar Dam (Site A)	Result at Kuhmaar Ke Naade Talab (Site B)
Evenness / Equitability index	0.916	0.9119
Dominance index	0.9673	0.9623
Dominance index approximation	0.9665	0.9609
Species Richness	58	44
Average population size	24.6731	16.8864
Simpson index	0.0327	0.0377
Simpson index approximation	0.0335	0.0391
Shannon Diversity index	3.62	3.45

Result and Discussion

Results of the field observation suggested that total 52 species of birds belong to 18 families and 10 orders distribution have been recorded at Ranjeet Sagar Dam in the study area. Among these families Ardeidae Wb and Anatidae Wb are the largest families represented by 8 species, followed by Rallidae Wb and Scolopacidae Wb families represent by 4 species Ciconiidae Wb, Threskiornithidae Wb, Charadriidae Wb, Recurvirostridae Wb families represent by 3 species Phalacrocoracidae Wb, Poenicopteridae Wb, and Motacillidae Wdb represent by 2 species each. Remaining families represent by single species. Order Sylviinae Wdb, Pelicaniformes family Ardeidae, order Anseriformes family Anatidae and order Charadriiformes family Charadriiformes showing equal percentage (13.79%) as well as highest percentage followed by order Gruiformes family Rallidae and order Passeriformes family Motacillidae have (6.90%), order Pelicaniformes family Threskiornithidae and order Ciconiiformes family Ciconiidae order Charadriiformes families Charadriidae and Recurvirostridae and order Coraciiformes family Alcedioidae stands with (5.17%), order Poenicopteriformes family Poenicopteridae order Suliformes family Phalacrocoracidae order Passeriformes family Sylviinae stands with (3.45%), while order Podicipediformes family Podicipedidae, Charadriiformes families Sternidae and Strigidae order Coraciiformes family Meropidae and order Passeriformes family have (1.72%) lowest percentage during study at Ranjeet Sagar Dam.

Total 44 species of birds belong to 17 families and 8 orders distribution have been recorded at Kuhmaar Ke Naade Talab. Ardeidae is largest family represented by 8 species followed by Anatidae Wb represent by 7 species, Rallidae Wb and Scolopacidae Wb represented by 4 species, Threskiornithidae Wb, Alcedioidae Wdb, represented by 3 species, Charadriidae Wb Recurvirostridae Wb Sylviinae Wdb represented by 2 species. Remaining families represent by single species. Order Pelicaniformes family Ardeidae showing highest percentage (18.18%) followed by order Anseriformes family Anatidae have (15.91%) order Gruiformes family Rallidae order Charadriiformes family Scolopacidae and order Passeriformes family Motacillidae have equal percentage (9.09%) order Pelicaniformes family Threskiornithidae, order Coraciiformes family Alcedioidae have percentage (6.82%) order Charadriiformes families Charadriidae, Recurvirostridae and order Passeriformes family Sylviinae have (4.55%) and order Cinconiiformes family Ciconiidae, order Charadriiformes family Sternidae order Coraciiformes family Meropidae order Passeriformes family Sylviinae have smallest percentage at Kuhmaar Ke Naade Talab.

The various diversity indices result for water birds and water associate birds shown in table 5. The highest value for Shannon-Weiner diversity index (H') was estimated to be (3.62) at Ranjeet Sagar Dam (Site A) followed by (3.45) at Kuhmaar Ke Naade Talab (Site B), where as Simpson's diversity index value was estimated to be (0.327) at (Site A) followed by (0.0377) at (Site B). Simpson's evenness (E) of birds species compares the similarity of the population size of each of the species which was estimated to be (0.916) at (Site A) followed by (0.9119) at (Site B) while species richness (n) was 52 at (Site A) followed by 44 at (Site B). The Dominance index values were observed approximate same value (0.9673). That values indicated the community of the water-birds at both study sites is highly diverse community.

Findings